

Speculation of Time and Space as Properties of a Particle and Quantum Mechanics

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In special relativity, energy and momentum are part of a 4-vector, but are also properties of a particle. X and t also form a 4-vector, but are not properties of a particle, but rather are measured relative to an external ruler or clock. Shifting the origin of the ruler/clock changes their value, but does not change the value of velocity and hence momentum. In (1), we called x and t running variables.

Special relativity deals with observations based on measurers in different frames moving at constant velocities. The ruler or clocks used by these people, however, may be shifted so there is no absolute property of time or x in this case either. Shifting a ruler or clock does not change the value of velocity, it is a property of the particle (assuming there are equally space gradations and clock intervals). In order to make x and t properties of a particle, we argue (as in (1)) that one may use $A = -Et + px$, a Lorentz invariant. For $-EE + pp$, ($c=1$), another Lorentz invariant, there is a link between all frames with rest mass squared ($c=1$). Within a specific frame (E, p exact numbers), $-Et + px$ creates a link between special degenerate (in terms of A) x and t points, i.e. $x + n \text{ constant}/p$ and $t + n \text{ constant}/E$. These keep A constant due to the minus sign. Thus E and p create an internal clock and ruler for a particle as we have argued in (1). This means that $n \text{ constant}/p$ are special “ x ” points (and the same with $n \text{ constant}/E$ and time) and suggests a probability distribution in x with a period of $\text{constant}/p$. Thus E and p interacting with x, t allow the latter to be properties of a particle, but at the cost of introducing probability.

Given the notion of probability, this suggests that entropy should come into play. One may ask: Is entropy maximized subject to a constraint? If so, what constraint should one use? We argue for a constraint of ipx associated with the period $\text{constant}/p$, the “ i ” being associated with periodicity. In such a case, the Lorentz invariant $-Et + px$ leads to $\exp(ipx)$ as a dynamic probability without the use of an eigenvalue equation.

Uncertainty in Special Relativity for x and t

Newtonian mechanics deals with deterministic quantities, x and t being two of them. The values of x and t , however, depend on clock/ruler values at the starting point. Shifting these values, shifts all x and t values. It does not, however, change the values of derivatives such as v or acceleration. There is no reason, we argue, to have clocks and rulers which are synchronized at some arbitrary starting point. This seems to have consequences in special relativity.

Special relativity deals with 4-vector values as seen from different constantly moving frames. (p, E) is an example of a 4-vector as is (x, t) . One may measure a vector in one frame and then use a Lorentz matrix to find the value as seen in a frame moving with constant $-v$ i.e.

$$\begin{vmatrix} 1/\sqrt{1-vv} & v/\sqrt{1-vv} \\ -v/\sqrt{1-vv} & 1/\sqrt{1-vv} \end{vmatrix} \quad ((1)) \quad c=1$$

Thus 4-vectors in a certain frame may be multiplied by ((1)) to find their value as seen in a frame moving with $-v$. This, however, assumes no arbitrariness in the ruler and clock initial times in

both frames. It is possible, however, for there to be shifts in a ruler and clock and there is no guarantee that a person in a moving frame originally synchronized his or her clock with a person, say in a rest frame. Thus although one may take an (x,t) vector in one frame and compute a specific new vector as seen from the $-v$ frame, there is always arbitrariness in x and t which does not exist for p and E . Thus x and t are not really properties of a particle because they are so dependent on the measuring device initial values. This leads to degeneracy as argued in (1).

If one considers the Lorentz invariant:

$$A = -Et + px \quad ((2))$$

then $t = t_0 + n \cdot \text{constant}/E$ and $x = x_0 + n \cdot \text{constant}/p$ lead to degeneracies i.e. the same A value as that associated with x_0, t_0 . Here n is the integer $0, 1, 2, \dots$ (One may note that the constant is \hbar in quantum mechanics and that $\hbar \rightarrow 0$ is considered the classical limit, i.e. the degeneracy is removed.)

The form $-E^2 + p^2$ (with the minus sign) ensures that all values of this quantity are equivalent to the rest frame value of $m_0^2 c^4$ where m_0 is rest mass. In the rest frame $p=0$ and E is considered to increase with motion, so as seen in a frame moving with $-v$, $E(v) > m_0 c^2$. Thus a minus sign is needed. This same minus sign, however, ensures that for a given frame (with fixed E, p values) E and p may create degeneracies in t and x with respect to the value A . These then treat certain x and t points in a special way (regardless of any shift in a ruler or clock). For this to occur, there must be a physical property which singles out the special x and t values, which would normally not be special for constant p i.e. constant velocity. We argue that this property is probability, i.e. an internal ruler and clock are created with 0 probabilities at the special x, t points.

Statistical Mechanics and Maximum Entropy

If there is probability associated with a particle moving with constant p , one may ask: Is entropy maximized for this motion? One may also ask, Why is p (momentum) and not velocity the criterion used? We argue that for this second question, one must consider the relevant information. From an impulse point of view, one cannot distinguish between different p values so they are equivalent even if they represent different velocities and rest masses.

In previous notes, we have associated the idea of special x points with an eigenvalue equation: $-i\hbar/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx)$. Here we wish to consider classical statistical mechanical arguments. In general, the idea of maximizing Shannon's entropy $- \int P_1(p,x) \ln(P_1(p,x))$ subject to a constraint should yield a probability distribution for the constant p particle. The question is: What is the constraint? Certainly p and $E = p^2/2m$ are constants, but there is a further constraint of periodicity i.e. integrating $x \cdot \text{probability}$ over a certain period should have a constant value. In fact, one may use the value px as it appears in $-Et + px$. In such a case, we propose maximizing:

$$- \int P_1(px) \ln(P_1(px)) + b \int ipx P_1(x) \quad ((3))$$

The “i” introduces periodicity. The solution of ((3)) is: $P_1(px) = \exp(i b px)$. It seems there is no reason for b and it may be set to 1.

Thus there is a two dimensional periodic probability in px. If one is unable to resolve the length constant/ $p = \hbar/p$, then it is as if one has smooth motion in x. Experiments (such as the 2 slit one) are able to resolve the periodicity.

Minimal Ground State Energy

There is a second statistical consequence of the px intervals i.e. wavelength. Classically one may have a particle with $p=0$ at $x=0$, but the wavelength \hbar/p becomes infinite for $p \rightarrow 0$. Thus to have a low p and localize the particle, one does not have energy 0. (The time-independent Schrodinger equation gives the exact ground state energy.) This suggests non-continuous energies which is in keeping with the idea of 0 entropy as Temperature $\rightarrow 0$ because a particle (or all particles) must be in a discrete ground state. Thus it seems that quantum mechanics has very strong ties to classical statistical mechanics/thermodynamics.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that x,t do not appear to be properties of a particle because they are measured by rulers and clocks which may have shifted origins. The Lorentz invariant $A_1 = -E^2 + p^2$ contains a minus sign because it links all A_1 values from different frames to the rest frame value $-m^2 c^4$ ($c=1$). In a given frame, however, “linking” might occur for different variables due to the minus sign i.e. $A = -Et + px$. For $t = t_0 + \text{constant} \cdot n/E$ and $x = x_0 + \text{constant} \cdot n/p$ where n is an integer, one has degeneracy in A. Thus there are special x and t points. If these have physical meaning, they must be distinguished from other x,t points. We suggest this is done through probability. How does one calculate this probability? We argue one should consider maximizing Shannon’s entropy with a constraint. The constraint needs to take into account the periodicity px which already includes the constraint of a constant p. We suggest maximizing: $-P_1(px) \ln(P_1(px)) + ipxP_1(x)$, with “i” indicating periodicity. This leads to the complex (two-dimensional) probability $\exp(ipx)$ which is the free particle wavefunction.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Energy and Momentum and T and Space X Running Variables ? (preprint, zenodo, 2023)